

THE ROLE OF COGNITIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The current article is devoted to teaching a foreign language through cognitive approach, which is teaching the students a language through making them think and reflect on what they have learned in order to be able to apply it further. As the language is a means of conveying and receiving some message, it is recommended that teachers should facilitate learning by helping the learners to construct their own language system. Making them repeat after a teacher without comprehending how the language works should be avoided as the learners are supposed to use the language consciously so that they will be able to produce and receive the language appropriately. Also, the difference between behaviorism and constructivism are investigated. It explores the ways of facilitating learning via constructing knowledge. In order to achieve this, the methods and techniques are suggested in this article.

Foreign language acquisition has become one of the demanded domains in the educational system of Uzbekistan. In order to achieve this, it is important to raise the effectiveness of the lessons so that the students will be able to master the language. A lot of methodologies, approaches, techniques and strategies have been suggested by different researchers so far. However, there is an issue how to make the lesson more authentic and guide the students so that they will be able to link their previous knowledge with the current one and construct their own language system. As there is evidence that learners tend to treat the pieces of knowledge separately unless teachers are skillful in selecting the tasks and approaches to teaching which

lead learners to construct one's own language system as possessing one's own language system is one of the crucial elements of acquiring the language and exploiting the language successfully. Therefore, language teachers encounter the issue of getting the students to build their own language system rather than to have them do the exercises and tasks without making sense what and why they are doing it and how this piece of information can be treated in their further academic performances.

Promoting language learning is a process where a teacher is supposed to design the lesson so that students will be able to use the target language, improve their skills and enhance their knowledge, learn the

ways of exploiting the target language autonomously and overall get something new from the lesson. Much research has been carried out on the principles of promoting foreign language learning to achieve all aforementioned results. According to Kerri-Lee Krause, a teacher should be careful in selecting input so that classrooms respect and incorporate the cultures of the learners and their families in the classroom while helping them to realize and feel the new culture of the community, the school, and the classroom. It is also argued that language teachers are supposed to bring extensive language input and provide the students with opportunities for output which results in students' development of perceptive and production. They also state collaboration with active engagement should be promoted so that they feel enjoyment and develop their interpersonal skills. Also, a teacher is supposed to introduce a variety of learning strategies, as well as reading, writing, speaking and listening strategies; formulaic expressions and rules to promote accuracy and fluency in dealing with a language. Moreover, language learning is integrated with meaningful, relevant, and useful content, generally the same academic content that is appropriate for the age and grade of learners. Emphasize the importance, relevance, and integration of theory and knowledge with professional practice to develop solutions to real world issues. Furthermore focus on meaning is supposed to be ensured, and attention is paid to the words' pragmatic meaning as working with pragmatic meaning of the words is vitally important in acquiring second language. Finally and most significantly, link with the prior knowledge must be thoroughly

emphasized to get students construct their own language system. To achieve this, teachers help learners use their prior knowledge of language, content, and the world to increase knowledge and develop it. All these principles serve for the successful foreign language learning and a teacher needs to be skillful enough to implement these strategies to have a fruitful lesson. The current article looks into the ways of linking the prior knowledge to the current one that is one of the psychological approaches to teaching and learning- Cognitive Constructivist approach.

Educational psychologists Marion Williams and Robert L. Burden consider being aware of 2 educational psychological approaches: behaviorism and cognitive approaches, and highlight making use and implementing cognitive constructivist approach as it leads learners to construct their own language system to master the language and become mature.

One of the approaches they mention is behaviorism - an approach where a teacher instructs to do something and students do it without thinking that is automatically, which is helpful to memorize the items of language. B. F. Skinner explains that a structural pattern is presented as a stimuli and students respond being followed by the reinforcement of a teacher. With a command and supervision of a teacher a success is achieved: students memorize the structure or words. This approach is very effective for young learners to promote learning. Tasks like filling in the gaps, drills, audio-lingual methods can be examples for this approach.

However, in contrast to behaviorism, cognitive constructivist approach is concerned with the way that human mind

thinks and learns in which people construct their knowledge structure through their understanding, and this understanding differs within each person. People tend to think whether to accept the information and refuse it by looking for links and evidences in their knowledge structure. Olena Vovk in her article entitled "Communicative and Cognitive Approach to Teaching English to University Students" points out the fundamental idea of the cognitive approach is that "the learning process should be aimed at acquiring (or rather inferring) knowledge, structuring and systematically arranging its units, storing and applying them while getting adapted to reality". Natalya Davidko emphasizes that the cognitive approach emphasizes the cognitive constructivist learning theory which is based on the concept that learning is an active individual process involving students' participation in knowledge acquisition. The constructivist theory came from George Kelly's idea of the 'personal construct' (internal models of the world) as the essential unit of mental cognitive structure that a person on purpose creates in the process of thinking and through which he understands, interprets, and evaluates events, situations, and new information. People with developed personal constructs — those that have a more complex organization and involve more associations among its elements, and for this reason are more differentiated and integrated — have greater expertise in a certain field. Experts differ from ordinary workers and novices in that they remember information from memory more quickly, organize and use it more quickly, and apply it to new situations reasonably. In fact, personal constructs differ from person to person

depending on his thinking abilities, learning styles, individual differences and affective factors. Since there is a challenge that knowledge may be built on faulty beliefs and misconceptions, the teacher's goal is to ensure that personal constructs don't differ much from the standard educational model and assist students to form more complex constructs step by step.

Cognitive approach highlights the idea of the conscious acquisition of language as a meaningful system. It carries importance not only to strengthen the learners' language skills but also polish up their communicative ability. It advocates the students to do the communicative activities creatively on the basis of understanding the new language material.

The objective of cognitive language teaching is the thinking, analyzing, classifying, and linking to the existing knowledge and many thinking competences. Taking into account the fact that learning a foreign or second language stretches the learner's understanding and insights into the world, the reasonable idea would be to combine the communicative and cognitive approaches and receive an approach, which integrates both communication and cognition. The reason for it comes the educational reality where an emphasis is given on the fact that students are enabled to respond to teachers' instructions and use the language. Nevertheless, the whole emphasis is supposed to be given on the fact that they should be urged to make sense of what they are speaking and their being able to use what they acquire not only in a situation by which they learned but also in other unfamiliar situations without any hesitation as they understand the item of

knowledge and have already linked to the knowledge they previously gained which leads to constructing their own language system where each item of knowledge is not treated separately but as one unit having many elements combined in relevance to each other. For this reason, the main objective of cognitive teaching a foreign language is the communicative and cognitive competence as a developed ability to perform speech and mental activity where a learner can have an opportunity to both practice his language skills and perform mental activities like criticizing, analyzing, synthesizing, making a creative approach and other mental activities in order to remember the target theme while learning the target language.

Also, this approach accounts for information processing, attention, memory process, intelligence and constructivism. Information processing involves the input-process- output process which is receiving information, working with it and acting upon it. Memory deals with the issues of learning and memorizing the words. The cognitive perspective implies that learning occurs through cognitive memory structures situated in the brain. These memory structures perceive process, store for short- or long-term periods and retrieve information. This approach acknowledges cause and effect links between learning and other cognitive processes like memory, motivation, personality and beliefs. It supports problem solving models of learning and avoids second reading approaches to new material.

As one of the principles of learning and teaching the language is that instructions should be focused predominantly on meaning, it can be concluded from the

above mentioned ideas that the cognitive view of learning which embodies the idea that information is gathered, processed and linked to the previously gained knowledge in our brain fulfills the requirements of the aforementioned principle.

There are several advantages of cognitive approach to education. Firstly, it is easy for people to understand and evaluate whether the information is worth studying that is it is possible to make the connections necessary to form new ideas and can be applied in future. Secondly, this way of looking at information makes sense to most people. By understanding learners will be able to use the gathered knowledge appropriately in other contexts. Another benefit is that teachers can organize activities that will help students learn by thinking which can enable the learners gain creativity. It is worth mentioning the creativity is one of the crucial elements of inventing, bringing about new ideas and advances to the target field which leads to further development. Next, constructivist view empowers students to follow their own interests and enhance learning through their interests. The widely known and accepted that learners learn best by the thing which are appealing to them. Also, it provides multiple experiences through which students are able discover and integrate information through direct involvement. The experiences presented to a given student change in response to the student's previous experiences, giving more advanced levels of involvement and more complicated concepts as the student's prior knowledge allows. Besides, it concentrates student's learning process and progress. If a student faces a challenge in understanding and mastering some process or concept, additional supportive

experiences are immediately designed in the mind or with the help of a teacher and provided to assist the child in achieving comprehension by which the student will be able to master that level before advancing on to the next level of cognitive development. Furthermore, in assistance with the cognitive approach, the students have an opportunity learn through a variety of new experiences. However, the essential thing is that during this learning process they use their existing knowledge to help them anticipate the outcome or infer what may happen next. Finally, this approach foregrounds a personalized learning which is one of the study skills as they all come with their own backgrounds and knowledge.

Respectively, to promote a cognitive constructivist approach in corporation with communicative approach, selecting tasks is crucially important as tasks serve to accomplish the aim of the lesson. In this approach tasks account for input – either written or spoken activities and cognitive operations, which are carried out by doing the activities. All these activities are reflected in the tasks chosen by a teacher. As a task is an activity “where the target language is used by the learner for a communicative purpose (goal) in order to achieve an outcome” , it has several features like a plan for learner activity; it involves a primary focus on meaning and real-world processes of language use; it can involve any of the four language skills; has a clear defined communicative outcome; and others to consider in designing the lesson plan. These features of the tasks highlight that task is supposed to engage cognitive processes to learn and teach the language so as to master it; there are

several tasks exposing the students to cognition that is learning by thinking.

To make teaching and learning more effective, as mentioned earlier cognitive constructivist approach in the education is presented best by providing tasks, issues and concepts in the form of problems rather than a piece of information presented in either oral or written form to be reproduced or find the answers in the text. To achieve fruitful results from the lesson, it is significant to select the tasks skillfully so that the learners will be able to get information, process it in their brain and link it with their previous knowledge and use it in other contexts.

There are several techniques that involve learners’ cognition. One of them is case study where a students is given a problematic case in which a students has to identify the problem(s) and find or recommend solution(s) to them. According to Bromley, D.B, a case study is an in-depth, detailed examination of a particular case (or cases) within a real-world context (. 1986). It is based on the real life or imaginary situation that demands analysis of the situation. In this technique a student will have an opportunity to practice his productive and receptive language skills in corporation with cognition through thinking and analyzing what the problem is and what caused it. Learners will be able to refer to their background knowledge to look at the situation logically and identify the problem. Moreover, to provide solutions, they will have to consider relevant issues they have encountered so far which serve to construct their language system. As case studies can be given either in written or spoken form, a student will be able to practice his reading or listening skills. After getting or understanding input

they will have to produce their output: they will either write or present their recommendation or resolutions to the problems in spoken form which generates the idea that students are enabled to practice their language skills and cognition in integration.

By applying this method the students are exposed to cognitive approach to teaching. It requires the learners that they look into the case themselves, identify the problem, and provide possible recommendations or solutions. They are considered effective because “by presenting content in the format of a narrative accompanied by questions and activities that promote group discussion and solving of complex problems, case studies facilitate development of the higher levels of Bloom’s taxonomy of cognitive learning; moving beyond recall of knowledge to analysis, evaluation, and application” (Bonney 2015, 21). Case studies are also advantageous for training learners of English as a foreign language (EFL) as the learners will have to think over the solution to a given case, be able to develop their linguistic skills in combination with analytical and/ or interpersonal skills. The reason for this is that the kind of situations can occur in “real life,” not in the educational context only.

Case studies can be modified to different language levels and teaching situations, such as English for specific purposes (ESP) or content-based learning (the context where the study of a subject matter dominated rather than linguistic skills). Contents may range from everyday issues to high-content cases requiring in-depth subject-matter knowledge. The more complex the case is, the more specific the knowledge and the more specialized the

language students will need. High-context cases are therefore suitable for learners who have sufficient proficiency in English and specialized knowledge about the subject. If teachers want to create their own subject specific case studies, they may consider the possibility of collaborating with a specialist subject teacher.

Here are general guidelines and steps for implementing a case study:

1. The situation should be described, not analyzed and be given in a narrative form.
2. Following questions should be addressed: Who are the main characters and what are their roles? What are the key problems and issues? What background information and relevant facts do others need to know to understand the case?
3. The case – the story should be coherent. There should be sufficient arguments so that the story will sound adequate. The relationship between cause and effect in the events must be clear, and the order of events must be easy for a reader to follow.
4. Supporting data needs to be provided if necessary (links to statistics, facts about the problem, a video that provides useful background information, etc.).
5. Paragraphs should be used to structure the information. One aspect of the story should be limited to the discussion in each paragraph and backed up with details. When it is necessary to discuss another aspect, it is recommended to start with a new paragraph.

The case-study method usually involves the following steps:

Step 1: The teacher introduces the situation and, if necessary, relevant vocabulary.

Step 2: Everyone reads the case study and analyzes additional materials.

Step 3: Students discuss possible solutions, usually in small groups.

Step 4: Students present and justify the solutions, usually with the whole class.

Step 5: Everyone participates in a feedback session, typically led by the teacher.

Step 6: Students reflect on the case study itself and on the procedure.

The duration of each step, particularly the reading and discussion stages, depends on the length and complexity of the case study.

The following issues should be considered before implementing case studies:

1. The case study should be realistic and complex enough with sufficient facts and background information, and with the provision of essential supporting documents to solve the case.

2. The manner how solutions will be presented—through whole-class discussions, with presentations, or in a final report should be clearly stated.

3. The cases should correspond to students' linguistic competence, prior knowledge and motivation so that they will be able to understand the language and situation itself reflected in the case.

4. The assessment criteria should be introduced in advance highlighting what skills will be assessed.

When a case study method is implemented in the EFL classroom one can witness that students will be able to develop their linguistic skills alongside with their critical thinking skills. They will be exposed to cognitive skills such as analyzing, synthesizing, arguing, evaluating and formulating through a cognitive approach to teaching. In addition, the teachers should be aware of the ways of implementing case studies in EFL

classroom and giving feedback to the learners' responses.

A teacher can use diversity of tasks to help students learn by thinking and constructing their own language system to master a foreign language. One of the types of tasks involving cognition is personalized learning approaches which focus on strengthening the student learning process by encouraging students to actively participate in creating a strong learning environment, becoming aware of their individual learning needs, and identifying and applying learning strategies that work best for them. Personalization is a significant approach to learning, because not every student learns in exactly the same way. In addition to helping students learn and become more focused on school, personalization can encourage students to think about the path they will follow after the lessons or university, i.e. intentions and plans for future. The other tasks are creating thoughtful environments by giving tasks like writing reflections on every lesson where the students write what they have learnt from the lesson after classes; bringing self-evaluation tests into the classroom which foster students thinking what kind of learners they are or what is their position in a given issue; introducing learning strategies by which learners can be aware how they learn best; fostering intertextuality that is working out what the author intends to say the text or discourse he has written in Discourse Analysis and Reading classes; teaching metaphors through cognition where the students will be able to interpret the meaning of metaphors by thinking and so on.

It is explicit from aforementioned facts and ideas, in learning a foreign language it important to construct one's own language

system which leads to understanding and being able to use the language in any situation rather than treating them as individual units of language. To achieve

this, teachers are recommended to be aware and make use of cognitive constructivist approach in integration with communication.

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